

#CollaborativeCarbon

Collaborative Carbon

Quantifying the Whole Life Carbon Potentials of Collaborative Housing Models across Europe

Synthesis, insights, and recommendations

May 2026

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RISE x einszueins // www.collaborative-carbon.com

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Info

Title	#CollaborativeCarbon: Whole Life Carbon Assessments for Collaborative Housing across Europe
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Problem & Opportunity

Problem

- Europe needs Affordable Housing and address the Climate Crisis
- Climate Impacts of Buildings are to reduce substantially (EPBD)

Opportunity

- Collaborative Housing models are perceived as promising solution
- Evidence suggests social, economic, and environmental (?) benefits

Questions

- What is Whole Life Carbon Performance of Collaborative Housing?
- Which WLC potentials exist and why? How can they be activated?

Long List: Collaborative Housing across Europe

- **329 CH projects compiled & contacted**
Long list: identified and invited for survey

Cases by City

Cases by Country

Short List: Whole Life Carbon Screening of CH

- **59 CH Projects for WLC Screening**
(70 projects responded & reviewed)

Cases by City

Cases by Country

Short List: 59 CH Projects

Short List: WLC Screening – Results Overview

Methodology

- Using EU WLC Benchmarks (kgCO₂e/m²) [[Ramon et al.](#)]
- WLC Screening based on CH project info (from survey)
- WLC/m² reflect benchmarks; WLC total and WLC/cap are project specific and relevant

Key Metrics

- (Average) Floor Area (m²/cap)
- WLC Emissions (kgCO₂e/cap)

Per Capita: Whole Life Carbon vs. Average Floor Area

CH Projects

Trends

Focus

Short List: Floor Area Metrics (m^2_{UFA})

Results

- Number of users
 - 83 users
- Unit size (avg)
 - 68.5 m^2
- Individual space (avg)
 - 29.9 m^2 (per user)
- Enjoyable space (avg)
 - 519.2 m^2 (per user)
- Based on 59 cases (short list)

	Number of users	Average unit size (UFA)	Average individual space	Average enjoyable space
mean	83.08	68.52	29.85	519.32
max	480.00	238.00	74.00	2982.00
90p	168.00	107.30	46.60	884.20
75p	91.00	84.00	40.00	610.50
50p	60.00	67.00	30.00	330.00
25p	32.50	48.50	23.00	175.50
10p	17.00	18.70	6.00	122.00
min	4.00	0.00	0.00	54.00

Short List: WLC Emissions (kgCO₂e/cap)

	Embodied Carbon (A, B, C)	Production (A1-3)	Construction (A4-5)	Replacement (B4)	Operation (B6)	Deconstruct (C1-2)	End of life (C3-4)
mean	25.54	19.77	2.13	1.88	31.30	0.59	1.17
max	108.95	81.48	8.00	9.77	172.49	2.25	7.45
90p	44.38	36.11	3.91	3.57	68.55	0.98	3.27
75p	33.75	25.55	2.82	2.08	40.42	0.84	1.78
50p	21.72	17.45	1.89	1.44	22.17	0.49	0.20
25p	11.42	9.30	0.90	1.02	12.09	0.30	0.10
10p	8.06	6.15	0.70	0.16	5.97	0.18	0.07
min	6.02	4.86	0.47	0.05	2.27	0.05	0.03

Short List: 59 CH Projects

Selection: 10 CH Projects

Selection: In-Depth LCA Modelling & Analysis

2x Conventional
(Vienna, AT)

Selection: In-Depth LCA Modelling & Analysis

Analysis: Conventional vs. CH Lighthouse

01 TRIO.inklusiv
AT einszueins architektur

02 OASE.inklusiv
AT einszueins architektur

03 Wohnprojekt Gleis 21
AT einszueins architektur

Analysis: Conventional vs. CH Lighthouse

Analysis: WLC Potentials within CH Projects

04 KooWo
AT Schwarz-Platzer Architekten

renovation of existing building

COLLA

* rise

sure
eins

05 Cirerers
ES Celobert cooperativa

06 La Chalmeta
ES Pau Vidal + Vivas Arquitectos

Analysis: WLC Potentials within CH Projects

Analysis: WLC Potentials within CH Projects

04 KooWo

Sharing of spaces:
NFA: 3 266m²

COLLA
* rise

sun
eins 00 ground floor

05 Cirerers

Sharing of spaces:
NFA: 2 118m²

05 fifth floor

02 second floor

00 ground floor

06 La Chalmeta

Sharing of spaces:
NFA: 2 902m²

07 seventh floor

02 second floor

00 ground floor

Dashboards: EC Details & Material Intensity

EMBODIED EMISSIONS

Project name: Wohnprojekt Gleis 21
Architects: einszueins architektur

GWP A1-A3 per GFAag	
emissions	270
storage	-99
kgCO ₂ e/m ² GFAag	
171	
GWP A1-A3 per NFAag	
emissions	310
storage	-114
kgCO ₂ e/m ² NFAag	
196	

General:
Country: Austria
Region: Vienna
Finished: 2019
Typology: Mixed use
Structure: frame wood

Area:
GFA total(ag+bg): 5 461 m²
above ground: 4 507 m²
below ground: 944 m²
NFA total(ag+bg): 4 701 m²
above ground: 3 824 m²
below ground: 777 m²
Ratio NFA/GFA: 86 %

Sharing spaces (by NFA total):
Individual: 55 %
Shared: 27 %
community: 8 %
Infrastructure: 19 %
Commercial: 11 %
Other: 8 %

Usage:
Number of users: 77
Average unit size: 78 m²
Average individual area: 33 m²
Average enjoyable area: 428 m²

Synthesis: Whole Life Carbon Potentials of CH

- **Collaborative housing (CH) can reduce Whole Life Carbon (WLC):** decisive factors are building typology, structural system and material choices, spatial organisation and sharing - all influence final whole life cycle emissions outcomes
- **Key elements of CH align with and support sustainable construction practices:** sustainable materials, energy efficiency AND efficient layouts, shared spaces
- **Scaling potential: Best-practices can be replicated to achieve WLC benefits** for both projects driven bottom-up (intentional CH) or top-down (municipal/national)
- **Opportunity: Affordable and sustainable housing policy and practice** can draw on the spatial and material lessons to improve WLC outcomes, learning from best practice CH and low carbon projects - with or without following strict CH definition

Key Findings: Floor Space Efficiency

- **Shared Luxury**

Through intentional, community-centred design, efficient and shared use of spaces, CH users can get an **enjoyable space 3–30× the floor area of users individual space^a**

- **Individual Sufficiency**

At the same time, **pioneering CH projects achieve 22–53% reduction^b** in average **floor area per user** compared to national averages (m²/cap) – saving resources & emissions.

a) Enjoyable space = individual space (i.e. apartment, per person) + shared spaces (e.g., community kitchen, workshop, sauna, etc.)

b) Comparing CH shortlist space use metrics with respective national average residential floor area per user ([Entranze](#))

Key Findings: Whole Life Carbon

- **CH WLC Savings:**

Low-carbon CH can save >1.000 tCO₂e embodied emissions per 100 people compared to new construction of conventional housing projects (average)^a

- **Housing Europe:**

Scaling best practice **low-carbon CH models to all new housing construction** across Europe could unlock **embodied carbon emission savings of >25 MtCO₂e annually**^b (~30% of embodied emission from EU's annual new residential building construction)

a) Based on shortlist WLC results: Saving 13 to 7 tCO₂e per person (25 to 40%); based on 19 tCO₂e/cap (A1-A3) to 25 tCO₂e/cap (A/B/C) in this study (shortlist WLC screening) vs. 32 tCO₂e/cap found elsewhere ([EU-ECB](#)). Capturing a similar amount of emissions (1.000 tCO₂) requires ~1.500 urban trees to grow for 10 years ([EPA](#)).

b) Considering baseline of 16.086 Mio m² New Residential Construction Permitted in 2020 ([BSO](#)) with related embodied carbon emissions of 79.01 Mt CO₂e ([WLC-Scenario-Explorer](#)). Applying potential per capita savings yields >25 MtCO₂e (19,75 to 31,50).

Future Research Potential

- **Clarify which specific elements of CH definitions meaningfully influence WLC performance** vs. those with limited impact – a systematic mapping is still missing
- **Investigate role of CH environmental values and resident-driven procurement** in making adoption of sustainable construction practices more likely in CH practice
- **Explore potential of CH as social enabler of low-carbon construction** – not as a technical driver, but demand-side force increasing probability of sustainability
- **Examine how findings from best-practice housing generalise to other contexts** – to different housing delivery models, climate conditions, or building cultures (e.g. learning from best in class public housing projects and WLC results (Vienna, etc.))

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Supplementary Information

Context, Methods, Insights

It takes a village... Kudos to the team!

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Context

- **Housing Crisis: Lack of Affordable, Sustainable Housing Options**
- Collaborative Housing (Cohousing) conceived as a Potential Solution
- Strong alignment with EU policy priorities and frameworks such as NEB
- Potential benefits on whole life carbon (WLC), relevant for new EPBD policies

<https://world-habitat.org/insight/collaborative-housing/>
<https://repositum.tuwien.at/bitstream/20.500.112708/213798/5/Peer-2025-Co-Creating%20Collaborative%20Housing%20Communities%20%20A%20Guidebook-vor.pdf>

Framework

WP1 EU case study compilation (long list) and WLC screening

Typology-based WLC screening

Quantitative WLC estimates (m2/cap)

WP2 WLC assessment of case study selection (short list)

Detailed whole life carbon analysis

WLC contributions from elements and spaces

WP3 Analysis of drivers, synthesis, and reporting

User consultation and analysis of drivers

Synthesis, reporting

Insights, learnings and recommendations

WP4 Project management and communications

Methodology & Objectives

- **Methods and materials**

- Two-step assessment process - **Objectives:**
 - **WP 1: WLC screening of ~100 collaborative housing projects** across Europe
 - **WP 2: Detailed WLC assessment of a short list of 10–20** selected projects
- Data collection process includes
 - gathering data on a broad range of projects focusing on key attributes data points describing the communities and their buildings including attributes on
 - building administration and localization, characterization of building typology, **quantification of floor area (m²) with different types of use, number of users, ...**
 - classification of building structure/materials and energy systems as a basis for whole life carbon (WLC) analysis.
- Quantification of **WLC results will be provided as per m² as well as per capita** values to enable comparison with relevant benchmarks on embodied and whole life carbon.

- **Expected Outcomes**

- Results are expected to provide quantitative evidence and arguments for scaling collaborative housing projects as an effective strategy to meet climate targets through community-led climate action in Europe and beyond.

WP1 - Method: Survey for longlist projects

- WP1: EU case study long list and WLC screening
 - Prepare research info sheet for contacting CH projects
 - Compile long list of collaborative housing projects
 - Send survey/questionnaire on project attributes

CO-LA
Whole Life Carbon Assessment for Collaborative Housing across Europe

is a new initiative that aims to establish a quantitative baseline for whole life carbon (WLC) assessment of collaborative housing projects in Europe.

Why it's important
As part of a research process, such as the European Commission Funding Scheme (ERC) and the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD), include requirements to report Whole Life Carbon (WLC) emissions of new buildings from 2023/2026 onwards. In addition, the 2024 Sustainable Finance Taxonomy is intended to channel funding towards sustainable climate solutions. However, the document opened the benefits of collaborative housing has focused primarily on the social and economic benefits and has left a gap in understanding of the potential climate and environmental benefits. This initiative will start to fill this gap by quantifying the environmental impact of collaborative housing projects across Europe.

Methodology
A multi-stage assessment process is applied, starting with a WLC screening analysis of around 100 collaborative housing projects across Europe, followed by a detailed WLC assessment of a short list of 20 selected projects. The process begins by gathering data on a broad range of projects housing on key attributes and data points describing the communities and their building including attributes on building administration and location, characteristics of building typology, quantification of floor area (m²) with different types of use, number of units, as well as installation of building energy related and energy systems as a basis for whole life carbon (WLC) analysis. The quantification of WLC results will be provided as per m² of use or per capita values to enable comparison with relevant benchmarks in embedded and whole life carbon.

Outcomes
The results are expected to provide quantitative evidence and arguments for scaling collaborative housing projects as an effective strategy to meet climate targets through community-led climate action in Europe and beyond.

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CO-LA
Whole Life Carbon Assessments for Collaborative Housing across Europe

Nr	Project Name	Country	Year of construction	Architects	Website	Contact & Tel/Email
1	Wohngemeinschaft Wien	Austria	2019	einszeuereins architektur sandwichler architekten	Sandwichler Architekten	office@einszeuereins.com +43 1 52722900
2	Gartenheim	Austria	2025			
3	Caribians Community Project	Austria	2017	N/A		N/A
4	Colonying Hofmeister	Austria	2023	Connet Filter		office@connetfilter.at
5	Gewiss im Brand Lustenau	Austria	2025	Güler Plan		office@guelerplan.at
6	Großer Markt	Austria	2018	sandwichler architekten	Sandwichler	office@search.at +43 1 8237900
7	Wohngemeinschaft Hasendorf	Austria	2018	einszeuereins architektur		
8	die Auenweide	Austria	2022	einszeuereins architektur		
9	Gleis 21	Austria	2018	einszeuereins architektur		
10	HaasWirtschaft	Austria	2023	einszeuereins architektur		
11	Pegasus Seestadt Aspern	Austria	2018	baldassano Architektur		https://www.bing.com/search?q=georg+mauld+gb+baldassano+at+070+see+pagoda&form=QA&5457769+(oneoul)+43+1+8207900+sb+haas-wirtschaft
12	Treibhaus Donaufeld	Austria	2026	sandwichler architekten		mb@baldassano.at
13	Kurbelstraße	Austria	2029	pos Architektur		office@pos-architekten.com +43 1 8181000
14	WOAL	Austria	2028	DIL		office@dil-woal.at +43 009 11 88 96 62
15	Quartiershaus "am Stadlbaaken"	Austria	2023	transparadio		office@transparadio.com +43 1 81 80 724
16	Wohngemeinschaft Rieseeggarten	Austria	2028	baldassano Architektur		mb@baldassano.at +43 1 8181000 5457769 (oneoul) 43 070
17	Assemblage Niklas Erlam	Austria	2024	RIM Architektur		office@rim-architektur.at +43 1 900932

CO-LA
Whole Life Carbon Assessment for Collaborative Housing across Europe

general information

Project picture
Name of Project:

Architects
Name of Community:

location
Country of Construction:

City or region (state, county) the case study building is located in:

Project address:

Year of construction completion
Building sub typology:

Project type/concept with implications on scope of the assessment:

structural information
Structural system description
Structure type:

Main material
vertical: horizontal: below ground:

Structure
with: columns: floor slabs, roof: basement (if any):

Insulation
facade, external walls: roof, basement:

Facade finishing

WP1 – Method: Data Collection & Selection

Method: Floor area definitions

Gross floor area (GFA); Useful floor area (UFA)
Individual / Shared / Commercial / Other

above / below ground

Method: Floor area definitions

Gross floor area (GFA); Useful floor area (UFA)
Individual / Shared / Commercial / Other

Enjoyable Space

above / below ground

WP2 – Method: Selection Criteria

Criteria

- Country
 - AT, CH, DE, ES, FR, UK
- Context
 - Urban, Rural, Outskirts (Vorstadt)
- Typology
 - SFH, MFH, ABL, Mixed
- Density
 - Low (1–2 floors), medium (3–6 floors), high (7–X floors)
- Size (m² floor area)
 - <500 m² / <1.000 m² / <1.500 m² / <2.000 m² / ...
- Data availability
 - Building info, plans, build-ups, EPCs - For conducting detailed BIM modelling & in-depth whole cycle assessment (LCA)

Context: Embodied emissions per capita

- Towards Embodied Carbon Benchmarks – Baseline
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5895050>

Embodied carbon per capita (harmonized) by building use subtype for EU-ECB

Context: Floor area per capita

- Average floor area per capita <https://entranze.enerdata.net/> (2008)

Context: Europe housing tenure

- Living conditions in Europe - Housing
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?oldid=669895>

Population distribution by tenure status at EU level, 2023

Source: Eurostat (online data code: ilc_lvho02)

eurostat

Context: Austria space by tenure

- Housing conditions (Statistics Austria)

<https://www.statistik.at/en/statistics/population-and-society/housing/housing-conditions>

⊖ Average living space per dwelling and per person by legal basis of dwelling 2024 (table)

Legal basis	Number of dwellings (main residences) in 1 000	Average living space per dwelling in square metres	Average living space per person in square metres	Average number of rooms per dwelling	Average number of rooms per person
House owner	1 506.8	146.6	56.2	5.1	2.0
Flat owner	485.9	86.8	43.9	3.5	1.8
Tenancy in communal flats	283.9	60.8	30.2	2.7	1.4
Tenancy in cooperatives flats	694.6	69.9	36.2	3.0	1.5
Other primary tenancy	808.7	70.6	36.1	2.9	1.5
Other legal basis	378.6	97.3	57.2	3.9	2.3

Q: STATISTIC AUSTRIA, Microcensus Housing 2024. Compiled on 18 March 2025.

Context: Housing emissions (operation) & cost

- Housing in Europe – 2023 edition
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/interactive-publications/housing-2024>

Greenhouse gas emissions by households for heating and cooling
(in kg per capita)

Source: Eurostat - [access to dataset](#)

Housing cost overburden rate in cities and rural areas, 2022
(in %)

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